

Make Some Energy: Tangible and Interactive Chemical Reactions

Hana Pokojná
hpokojna@mail.muni.cz
Visitlab, Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic

Barbora Kozlíková
kozlikova@mail.muni.cz
Visitlab, Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic

Simone Kriglstein
kriglstein@mail.muni.cz
HCILab, Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
Vienna, Austria

Daniel Echeverri
daniel.echeverri@mail.muni.cz
Atelier of Graphic Design and Multimedia,
Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

We created an alternative way of presenting chemical reactions through tangible, interactive, and movable models. The adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis, often represented by written formulas, is problematic for high school students due to its complexity and abstract nature. We used real protein data to prototype a 3D-printed ATP synthase molecule adapted to move (e.g., a spinning motor). We then collected feedback from biomedical visualisation experts to improve our second prototype. Afterward, we created a tangible interactive electron transport chain and observed people interacting with it at a public outreach event. A combination of art, science, and technology allows the users to go beyond observing and explaining complex chemistry through tactile exploration, visuals, and minimal text at scientific museums and introductory classes in biochemistry.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Participatory design**.

KEYWORDS

Tangible objects, biochemistry visualization, interactive education, medical art

Reference Format:

Hana Pokojná, Simone Kriglstein, Barbora Kozlíková, and Daniel Echeverri. 2024. Make Some Energy: Tangible and Interactive Chemical Reactions. In *Proceedings of Expanded Animation Conference on Animation and Interactive Art (Expanded'24)*, September 5-7, Linz, Austria. 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13132327>

1 INTRODUCTION

Alternative visualisations of complex data enhance science accessibility and retention for laypeople, students, and experts [12]. Modern technology offers science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) teaching alternatives beyond traditional written formulas, including molecular animations [27–29], biochemistry virtual labs [48], and Augmented Reality (AR) for experimental chemistry [53]. New types of visualisations, such as the early 3D physical models of Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid (DNA) double helix [52], aided spatial understanding and influenced future research. The efficacy of physicalisations fuels ongoing research on their role in presenting science, understanding complex data, and education in diverse contexts [24, 34, 46].

Our project presents a set of interactive tangible molecular machines to foster biochemistry learning. Specifically, we chose to represent the electric transport chain Fig.1 (a), a series of chemical reactions that contribute to the energy-making process in all living organisms (Adenosine triphosphate synthesis- ATP synthesis) [4]. The final interactive prototype is intended for tactile and visual exploration and is based on an expert review of our prototype molecule (ATP synthase) and observation of non-experts interacting with the tangible chemical system (entire electron transport chain). The final physicalisations, inspired by medical art [15], are intended for introductory biochemistry classes and science museums.

2 BACKGROUND RESEARCH

The ATP synthesis is commonly studied at European high schools [30]; however, students often need help understanding it [13, 19] due to its abstract nature and inability to connect biology and chemistry knowledge [23]. The lack of understanding is also attributed to little comprehension of molecular structures [22] unseen in written formulas in Fig.1(b), which inspired us to apply this interactive visualisation technique to this particular chemical process.

Physicalisations exceed diagrams and animations by engaging more senses, evoking emotions [33], and promoting higher learning through hands-on interaction [25, 38], particularly for reasoning about abstract concepts [6]. Successful applications in an educational context of STEM subjects span across physics [37], pharmacology [17], veterinary sciences [11], bio-design [39], gene editing

Figure 1: (a) the ATP synthesis, including the electron transport chain and its respective enzymes. (b) written formula for this chemical reaction.

[51], and biochemistry [7]. Integrating virtual components and interactive layers introduces new forms of artistic expression, blending traditional art with technology. The aforementioned applications' success in education can be partly attributed to the attractive presentation, which plays a role in the learner's motivation [36].

In the biomedical field, physicalisations of molecules can help with understanding aspects that cannot be well observed on a screen [27], e.g., extending understanding of protein assembly [5] where tangibility helps experts with understanding of high dimensional structures [49]. Innovative examples of tactile exploration of the microbiological world include touch-screen interaction [32]. Research into chemistry education also shows that balls-and-sticks physical models outperformed applications that used interactive tangible interfaces [16], pointing to the benefits of tangibility. New playful approaches to studying biology have been invented, e.g., biotic video games [31] or cellular LEGO[®] blocks models [18].

2.1 Design considerations

Our design was inspired by medical art, which facilitates the understanding of complex scientific topics through artistic renderings [15]. In the case of the ATP synthesis, this was already demonstrated through different 2D media [43]. For 3D physical media, various materials (e.g., rubber [2], silicone, wood, and 3D printing) facilitate user assembly, enhancing familiarity with the chemical compound [40]. Molecular data from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) [45] enables the creation of accurate digital and physical models for molecules [1] or viruses [5]. The popularity and usefulness of physical 3D molecules in science education led to the development of an add-on for easier 3D printing of balls-and-sticks molecular

models [42] in Blender [10] software. One limitation of 3D-printed models is their static nature [12]. To address this, current research explores integrating virtual components to create tactile molecular interfaces [35]. Adding information involves overlays with virtual displays [47], including motion with projections or AR applications [8, 20, 21]. Another interaction layer enhances the 3D physical models through molecular puzzles for understanding binding [2, 7] or using LEGO[®] blocks for comprehending larger compound architecture [18]. However, a comparison [9] between AR and physical models in chemistry education favored physical models due to their tangible properties.

3 ENZYME DESIGN

As a first step, we have created a prototype of the most complex enzyme in ATP synthesis, the **ATP synthase**. This enzyme carries out the energy-creation step consisting of complex movements, e.g., enzyme rotations and interaction with other molecules, such as Hydrogen protons (**H⁺**) entering the motor, by which they rotate the axle, which leads to the creation of the ATP from Adenosine diphosphate (**ADP**) and Phosphate (**P**) molecules. This first physicalisation helped us to establish the standard for the following models. To create the ATP enzyme, we used data from PDB database [45], see Fig. 2 (a), to make a 3D digital model using 3DProteinImaging software [50] (Fig. 2 (b)) and refined it in Blender [10] to reduce vertices (Fig. 2 (c)) for optimized 3D printing and movement of the physical model (Fig. 2 (d)), e.g., axle rotation. The Lock-and-key model [2, 18] illustrated the formation of ATP from ADP and P molecules joining to form an ATP molecule in the enzyme's head and motor. This

approach required both technical and creative reasoning to make the model accurate, useful, and attractive.

3.1 Expert review of the ATP synthase

Our prototype was first evaluated by nine visualisation and biochemistry researchers, who gave us feedback on improving the model aimed at science dissemination. After interacting with the model and asking questions, they were asked to answer questionnaires consisting of 5-point Likert scales and short open-answer questions to gain insight into model improvements. The nine participants had an average of 8.89 years of experience (range 3–20), with backgrounds in visualisation, bioinformatics, human evolution, biophysics, and biology.

3.2 Results

Overall, the experts liked the 3D physical model (4.67/5) and found it helpful in learning about chemical reactions (4.22/5). The model captured their attention and sparked an interest to learn more (4.63/5), mainly because they could *touch molecules that are otherwise invisible or can be seen only through screens*. They stated that this type of presentation is more helpful than learning from biomedical animations (3.5/5) because *you can notice more things about the enzyme when you touch it as opposed to not noticing something in an animation*. However, it was mentioned that the physical model has a smaller outreach than the animation. Suggestions included that *ideally, the physical models would be combined with animations*. The participants also agreed that a 3D physical model is more helpful than learning from biomedical illustrations in this specific context (4/5) because it helps understand the shape of molecules. Based on the participants' answers, we concluded that the 3D model could be made of different materials or show subtle movements, such as the *quivering of the head, as they do in real life*. A suggestion was to create an immersive experience where visitors can enter the mitochondrial matrix, a room with several enzymes involved in the energy-making process and the electron transport chain.

3.3 Representations of the electron transport chain

The biochemical processes are often represented through written formulas or 2D diagrams typical for textbooks, similarly to depictions in Fig.1. Another helpful way of visualising molecular interactions is to offer spatial explanations of the movement of the molecules in 3D space [26, 28, 29]. Animation describing molecular motion in the electron transport chain [3] became a reference for creating the movements in tangible models, as it clearly shows molecular interactions. After gaining insight into the first 3D-printed chemical model from the experts, we designed the entire transport chain prototype. The electron transport chain transfers electrons across the phospholipid bilayer membrane through protein complexes [41]. This information is represented by 3D physical models that viewers can explore through touch. It includes the ATP synthase and the electron transport chain made of the **phospholipid bilayer, protein channels**, and protein **co-enzymes** within the bilayer that carry electrons between the proteins, and larger molecules interacting with the electron transport chain on both sides of the bilayer.

The phospholipid bilayer, a membrane that encapsulates the enzymes and separates the differently charged *Intermembrane space* and *Matrix* of the mitochondria, was modeled in Blender [10] and 3D printed. Then, the individual proteins were imported as .pdb data, turned into virtual models, and adjusted in 3D modelling software so the H⁺ cube-shaped protons could pass through them using a tunnel opening. The Intermembrane space is oriented at the top of the phospholipid bilayer, so the H⁺ cubes can be dropped down the hollow tunnel of the model, simulating their flow to the Matrix using gravity. The co-enzyme models were prepared from .pdb data in the same fashion as the ATP synthase and the proteins. In real life, they move within the phospholipid bilayer membrane. In contrast to accurate proteins and co-enzymes, the molecules in the electron transport chain model are shown with simple shapes. These molecules mainly combine with smaller ones, like H⁺ cubes, to form larger ones. Using a puzzle-like approach with lock-and-key models, [2, 18], the versatile H⁺ cube fits into crevices of various molecules, passing through the cube-shaped tunnels in protein channels. The ADP and P molecules create ATP molecules at a single attachment site. Water, H₂O, comprises two H⁺ molecules in the **O molecule**. The **FAD+** and **NAD+** are round, reflecting their structural similarity. The FAD⁺ is elongated, the NAD⁺ is spherical, and their size and shape prevent them from passing through channels meant for H⁺. The complete 3D printed complex is illustrated in Fig.3.

3.4 Non-expert review of the electron transport chain

The electron transport chain was added to the ATP synthase and presented as a completed prototype at Researcher's Night, an annual public outreach event for research institutions. This allowed us to observe the reactions of non-expert viewers interested in science to determine whether this presentation would interest them. Upon agreement, the viewers (aged 6-72) were given an explanation of the electron transport chain and ATP synthesis using simple terms, an illustration of mitochondria and a human cell, and the physical interactive model. They were encouraged to ask questions and touch the models while thinking aloud [14]. They were asked whether they would be interested in seeing this setup in a science museum or find it helpful to have it in science classes.

3.5 Non-expert results

Through observations, we saw a great interest in these representations. Out of the approximately fifty visitors, two viewers were medical students and commented that this model would be very useful for their studies in medical school. One of these two students stayed at the presentation station and continued to ask questions about the making of the model and commented that *... it would have been useful when I was learning chemistry*. One of the viewers was a high school biology teacher who used 3D digital models and mentioned that it is a very innovative way of displaying information and *even more helpful than animations*. A university professor teaching first-year medical students expressed an interest in the digital versions of the models so they can be 3D printed and used in a lesson at their university. Six children, aged 9-13, expressed interest in playing with the ATP synthase and spinning the motor

Figure 2: Development of the ATP synthase; (a) shows visualisation [50] of raw PDB [45] data with balls-and-sticks, (b) preview of enzyme model [50], (c) reduction of vertices from 4, 487 890 to 2, 357 136 vertices in [10], (d) the final 3D printed model (35cmx32x17cm).

and axle. A child aged 6 played with lock and key models. Questions were raised, such as *How big is this molecule in real life?* or *What does this do in our body?*

4 DISCUSSION

Extensive research into tangible interactive artifacts in education has proven beneficial, especially in STEM subjects, e.g., [2, 17, 37]. Modern-day technology allows us to create true-to-life models of molecules, otherwise unseen by the naked eye [1, 5]. Effective explanations of chemical reactions can be enhanced and made more exciting and understandable through tangible interactive artifacts [7]. Our model of ATP synthase was created with .pdb data [45] and movable components later evaluated by biomedical visualisation experts. Their suggestions led us to add an entire electron transport chain. This second prototype was then presented at a public outreach event to observe and determine whether this type of installation would interest people in biochemistry. This tangible approach would be helpful to people with dyslexia or sight impairments, who would bypass long texts with tangibles. In accordance with *exploration* [54] principles, which rely on the interaction between users and technology to understand various scientific observations, it would aid their understanding of molecular reactions. Allowing the general public to learn through interaction and visualisation has been proven helpful [44], demonstrated in scientific museums, e.g., Visualisation Centre C (Sweden), Exploratorium (USA), and VIDA! (Czechia). We attribute the users' positive feedback to the models' tangible and movable properties and informative presentation enhanced through the playful presentation of biochemistry [25, 33, 38]. We created a conceptual immersive cell space design based on this first expanded prototype developed through an iterative process. The joining of art, technology, and science would allow people to touch and be part of a molecule that is otherwise unseen to the naked eye. Making the models and videos is time-consuming; however, once they are completed, they can be installed in any museum. As proposed by one participant in the observational study

and their interest in models in their class, the digital .stl models can be sent directly to the educator, who just needs to print and assemble them. This also points to easy reproduction of the models and even updating the digital models. Another benefit is that interacting with the physical model can help the user notice some information (e.g., structural) they would otherwise miss in video format or 2D illustration [27, 49]. A shortcoming of 3D physical models is that you cannot 'zoom in or out' as the artifacts cannot be changed once they are 3D printed [12]. However, the digital models that precede the physical models can be easily altered, and more versions of the physical models can be delivered. In the future, it would be interesting to create an immersive experience that combines 2D illustrations [22], animation [27–29], and tangible models [25, 38], culminating into an installation that reaps benefits of all three modalities, as suggested in Appendix A (4). This immersive and tangible approach can be generalized to other chemical reactions like protein docking, motor proteins such as kinesin and myosin, DNA transcription, or nuclear pore complexes. Photosynthesis is another similar process that makes plant energy. Animal and cell respiration installation could be placed next to each other, pointing out the differences between the two processes, as they are often contrasted in high school textbooks. Furthermore, similar models could be made so that expert biochemists can show specific parts of the model when discussing specific compounds, such as nuclear pore complexes. Our research with non-experts has shown that people would be interested in using this representation in teaching, e.g., the university professor who enquired about the models and the high school biology teacher who mentioned that this tactile medium would be more useful than illustrations and animations. It would be interesting to provide these physical models to learning institutions in the future because pupils are first exposed to ATP synthase at the high school level [30]. It is deemed difficult for various reasons [13, 19, 22, 23] and conducting further studies, measured by test scores and enjoyment questionnaires, would give

Figure 3: Figure above shows the resulting 3D printed ATP enzyme in the context of the electron transport chain and its respective sub-parts: (a) protein channels, (c-d) molecules, and (e) co-enzymes.

more insight into whether these learning tools are helpful in the classroom and not just at public engagement events.

5 CONCLUSION

The tangible, interactive, movable, and immersive experience is an excellent alternative way to explain biochemistry processes to people new to biochemistry. As our iterative study demonstrates, art and technology allow us to provide scientific discoveries to everyone. The eye-catching and dynamic properties rooted in the artistic and engineering fields attract the viewer's attention and inspire them to learn more. If not used for education, the produced artifacts could serve as stand-alone organic sculptures. Overall, this process uses more senses and provides enjoyment to help understand abstract scientific processes that are otherwise invisible to the naked eye.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the participants for their valuable insights.

REFERENCES

- [1] Daniel Acevedo, Song Zhang, David H. Laidlaw, and Christopher W. Bull. 2004. Color Rapid Prototyping for Diffusion-Tensor MRI Visualization. In *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2004*, Christian Barillot, David R. Haynor, and Pierre Hellier (Eds.). Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1076–1078.
- [2] Thomas Alderighi, Daniela Giorgi, Luigi Malomo, Paolo Cignoni, and Monica Zoppè. 2021. Computational design, fabrication and evaluation of rubber protein models. *Computers & Graphics* 98 (2021), 177–187.
- [3] Prakash B. 2017. ELECTRON TRANSPORT CHAIN ANIMATION. Retrieved December, 2022 from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nCr3iCzX4lc>
- [4] James Baddiley, Alan M Michelson, and Alexander Robertus Todd. 1948. Synthesis of adenosine triphosphate. *Nature* 161, 4098 (1948), 761–762.
- [5] Michael J Bailey, Klaus Schulten, and John E Johnson. 1998. The use of solid physical models for the study of macromolecular assembly. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology* 8, 2 (1998), 202–208.
- [6] Saskia Bakker, Elise Van Den Hoven, and Alissa N Antle. 2010. MoSo tangibles: evaluating embodied learning. In *Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. 85–92.
- [7] Olivier Biner, Thomas Schick, Aymar Abel Ganguin, and Christoph von Ballmoos. 2018. Towards a synthetic mitochondrion. *Chimia* 72, 5 (2018), 291–291.
- [8] Simon Brenner. 2015. *Projector-based textures for 3d-printed models*. Ph. D. Dissertation.
- [9] Yu-Chien Chen. 2006. A study of comparing the use of augmented reality and physical models in chemistry education. In *Proceedings of the 2006 ACM international conference on Virtual reality continuum and its applications*. 369–372.
- [10] Blender Online Community. 2018. *Blender - a 3D modelling and rendering package*. Blender Foundation, Stichting Blender Foundation, Amsterdam. <http://www.blender.org>
- [11] Margaret Cook, Jinsil Hwaryoung Seo, Michelle Pine, and Annie Sungkajun. 2018. Paper Circuitry and Projection Mapping: An Interactive Textbook Approach to Veterinary Education. In *Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 131–135.
- [12] Pierre Dragicevic, Yvonne Jansen, and Andrew Vande Moere. 2020. Data physicalization. *Handbook of human computer interaction* (2020), 1–51.
- [13] Benjamin W Dreyfus, Vashti Sawtelle, Chandra Turpen, Julia Gouvea, and Edward F Redish. 2014. A Vision of Interdisciplinary Education: Students' Reasoning about "High-Energy Bonds" and ATP. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1402.5408* (2014).
- [14] David W Eccles and Güler Arsal. 2017. The think aloud method: what is it and how do I use it? *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health* 9, 4 (2017), 514–531. <https://doi.org/10.1109/47.867942>
- [15] Caroline Erolin. 2020. Medical illustration in the 21st century and beyond. *Medical Writing* 29 (2020), 6–10.
- [16] Morten Fjeld, Jonas Fredriksson, Martin Ejdestig, Florin Duca, Kristina Bötschi, Benedikt Voegtli, and Patrick Juchli. 2007. Tangible user interfaces for chemistry education: comparative evaluation and re-design. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems*. 805–808.
- [17] Simon Ford and Tim Minshall. 2019. Invited review article: Where and how 3D printing is used in teaching and education. *Additive Manufacturing* 25 (2019), 131–150.
- [18] Claire Louise Palmer Garden. 2022. Lego Serious Play: Building engagement with cell biology. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education* 50, 2 (2022), 216–228.

- [19] CG Gayford. 1986. Some aspects of the problems of teaching about energy in school biology. *European Journal of Science Education* 8, 4 (1986), 443–450.
- [20] Alexandre Gillet, Michel Sanner, Daniel Stoffler, David Goodsell, and Arthur Olson. 2004. Augmented reality with tangible auto-fabricated models for molecular biology applications. In *IEEE Visualization 2004*. IEEE, 235–241.
- [21] Alexandre Gillet, Michel Sanner, Daniel Stoffler, and Arthur Olson. 2005. Tangible augmented interfaces for structural molecular biology. *IEEE computer graphics and applications* 25, 2 (2005), 13–17.
- [22] David S Goodsell. 2009. The machinery of life. , 351–402 pages.
- [23] Abigail I Green, Kristin N Parent, Sonia M Underwood, and Rebecca L Matz. 2021. Connecting ideas across courses: relating energy, bonds & how ATP hydrolysis powers a molecular motor. *The American Biology Teacher* 83, 5 (2021), 303–310.
- [24] Sarah Hayes. 2018. Exploring the Potential of Data Physicalization for STEM Learning. In *Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 703–705.
- [25] Fabian Hutmacher and Christof Kuhbandner. 2018. Long-term memory for haptically explored objects: fidelity, durability, incidental encoding, and cross-modal transfer. *Psychological science* 29, 12 (2018), 2031–2038.
- [26] Janet H Iwasa. 2015. Bringing macromolecular machinery to life using 3D animation. *Current opinion in structural biology* 31 (2015), 84–88.
- [27] Yvonne Jansen, Pierre Dragicevic, Petra Isenberger, Jason Alexander, Abhijit Karnik, Johan Kildal, Sriram Subramanian, and Kasper Hornbæk. 2015. Opportunities and challenges for data physicalization. In *proceedings of the 33rd annual acm conference on human factors in computing systems*. 3227–3236.
- [28] Jodie Jenkinson. 2018. Molecular biology meets the learning sciences: Visualizations in education and outreach. *Journal of molecular biology* 430, 21 (2018), 4013–4027.
- [29] Jodie Jenkinson and Gaël McGill. 2012. Visualizing protein interactions and dynamics: evolving a visual language for molecular animation. *CBE—Life Sciences Education* 11, 1 (2012), 103–110.
- [30] Mary Jones, Richard Fosbery, Jennifer Gregory, and Dennis Taylor. 2014. *Cambridge International AS and A Level Biology Coursebook with CD-ROM*. Cambridge University Press.
- [31] Amy T Lam, Jonathan Griffin, Matthew Austin Loeun, Nate J Cira, Seung Ah Lee, and Ingmar H Riedel-Kruse. 2020. Pac-Euglena: A Living Cellular Pac-Man Meets Virtual Ghosts. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 1–13.
- [32] Seung Ah Lee, Alice M Chung, Nate Cira, and Ingmar H Riedel-Kruse. 2015. Tangible interactive microbiology for informal science education. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 273–280.
- [33] Yanhong Li, Meng Liang, Julian Preissing, Nadine Bachl, Michelle Melina Dutoit, Thomas Weber, Sven Mayer, and Heinrich Hussmann. 2022. A meta-analysis of tangible learning studies from the tei conference. In *Proceedings of the Sixteenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 1–17.
- [34] Dan Lockton, Lisa Brawley, Manuela Aguirre Ulloa, Matt Prindible, Laura Forlano, Karianne Rygh, John Fass, Katie Herzog, and Bettina Nissen. 2019. Tangible thinking: Materializing how we imagine and understand systems, experiences, and relationships. (2019).
- [35] Xavier Martinez, Nicolas Férey, Jean-Marc Vézien, and Patrick Bourdot. 2019. 3D reconstruction with a markerless tracking method of flexible and modular molecular physical models: Towards tangible interfaces. *Journal of Virtual Reality and Broadcasting* 14, 2 (2019).
- [36] Richard E Mayer. 2014. Incorporating motivation into multimedia learning. *Learning and instruction* 29 (2014), 171–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016>
- [37] Andrea Miller, Claire Rosenbaum, and Paulo Blikstein. 2012. MagneTracks: a tangible constructionist toolkit for Newtonian physics. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded and Embodied Interaction*. 253–256.
- [38] Magdalena Novak and Stephan Schwan. 2021. Does touching real objects affect learning? *Educational Psychology Review* 33, 2 (2021), 637–665.
- [39] Johanna Okerlund, Evan Segreto, Casey Grote, Lauren Westendorf, Anja Scholze, Romie Littrell, and Orit Shaer. 2016. Synflo: A tangible museum exhibit for exploring bio-design. In *Proceedings of the TEI'16: Tenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 141–149.
- [40] Arthur J Olson. 2015. Self-assembly gets physical. *Nature nanotechnology* 10, 8 (2015), 728–728.
- [41] Thomas Ott, Joanne Clarke, Katharine Birks, and Giles Johnson. 1999. Regulation of the photosynthetic electron transport chain. *Planta* 209 (1999), 250–258.
- [42] Paul J Paukstelis. 2018. MolPrint3D: Enhanced 3D printing of ball-and-stick molecular models.
- [43] Hana Pokojná, Barbora Kozlíková, Drew Berry, Simone Kriglstein, and Katarína Furmanová. 2023. Seeing the unseen: Comparison study of representation approaches for biochemical processes in education. *Plos one* 18, 11 (2023), e0293592. <https://doi.org/10.1371>
- [44] Linda Ramey-Gassert, Herbert J Walberg III, and Herbert J Walberg. 1994. Re-examining connections: Museums as science learning environments. *Science education* 78, 4 (1994), 345–363.
- [45] rcsb PDB. 2006. RCBs Protein Data Bank. Retrieved April 3, 2024 from <https://www.rcsb.org/>
- [46] Kim Sauvé, Hans Brombacher, Rosa Van Koningsbruggen, Annemiek Veldhuis, Steven Houben, and Jason Alexander. 2023. Physicalization from theory to practice: Exploring physicalization design across domains. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 1–7.
- [47] Simon Stusak and Markus Teufel. 2014. Projection augmented physical visualizations. In *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM symposium on Spatial user interaction*. 145–145.
- [48] Athanasios Sypas and Dimitris Kalles. 2018. Virtual laboratories in biology, biotechnology and chemistry education: a literature review. In *Proceedings of the 22nd Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics*. 70–75.
- [49] Michael C Thrun and Florian Lerch. 2016. Visualization and 3D printing of multivariate data of biomarkers. (2016).
- [50] Gianluca Tomasello, Ilaria Armenia, and Gianluca Molla. 2020. The Protein Imager: a full-featured online molecular viewer interface with server-side HQ-rendering capabilities. *Bioinformatics* 36, 9 (2020), 2909–2911.
- [51] Clarissa Verish, Amanda Strawhacker, Marina Bers, and Orit Shaer. 2018. CRISPEE: a tangible gene editing platform for early childhood. In *Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*. 101–107.
- [52] James D Watson and Francis HC Crick. 1953. The structure of DNA. In *Cold Spring Harbor symposia on quantitative biology*, Vol. 18. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, 123–131.
- [53] Mikołaj P Woźniak, Adam Lewczuk, Krzysztof Adamkiewicz, Jakub Józiewicz, Maya Malaya, and Piotr Ladonski. 2020. Archemist: Aiding experimental chemistry education using augmented reality technology. In *Extended abstracts of the 2020 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. 1–6.
- [54] Anders Ynnerman, Jonas Löwgren, and Lena Tibell. 2018. Explorantion: A new science communication paradigm. *IEEE computer graphics and applications* 38, 3 (2018), 13–20.

A IMMERSIVE CELL CONCEPT

The illustration (Fig.4) describes the immersive cell concept.

B 3D MODELS

The digital 3D models used in this study can be retrieved from the OSF Repository under the project name 'Interactive ATP Synthesis'.

Figure 4: Figure describing a concept design of an immersive cell experience that consists of (a) interactive models that are described in this paper, accompanied by (b) contextual information like surrounding molecules shown through video projection, (c) detailed illustration of the mitochondria, and (d) the entire animal cell.